

The Thermal Runaway Phenomenon of Unipolar Power Semiconductors in Cryogenic Power Electronics

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Abstract—Galliumnitride (GaN) high electron mobility transistor (HEMT) and silicon metal-oxide semiconductor field effect transistor power devices exhibit greatly reduced conduction losses at cryogenic temperatures. Consequently, cryogenic cooling is currently largely investigated in aviation research. However these temperatures lead to a hitherto largely unnoticed, safety-critical phenomenon of “thermal runaway,” which becomes increasingly severe as the coolant temperature drops. This effect arises because the losses generated in the chip increase more rapidly with rising temperature than the heat that can be conducted away from the chip. Contrary to the well-known behavior at room temperature, a higher current density cannot be achieved by arbitrarily increasing the temperature swing. Instead, a tipping point is reached beyond which the system enters thermal self-destruction. Here, this effect is described theoretically and validated experimentally at liquid nitrogen temperatures using a GaN HEMT.

Index Terms—Cryogenic power electronics, thermal instability, thermal runaway (TR).

I. INTRODUCTION

ELECTRIC and hybrid-electric propulsion architectures are among the emerging technological innovations that promise a greener and more fuel-efficient aviation sector of the future. Due to the increasing demand for air travel due to population growth and prosperity, a 34 % increase in CO₂ emissions has been recorded from 2015 to 2020. The European Commission’s Green Deal pressures the aviation sector by requiring zero CO₂ emissions in all sectors by 2050. In 2020, the share of anthropogenic CO₂ emissions was approximately 2% to 3 %. With a projected growth rate of 4 % per year, drastic measures must be taken toward electrifying aircraft within different time horizons starting today [1], [2], [3], [4], [5], [6]. When comparing possible energy carriers for electric aircraft, state-of-art lithium-ion batteries cannot reach the gravimetric

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energy density of hydrogen, which is one of the main parameters defining the range of the aircraft. Therefore, fuel cell aircraft [7], [8] using cryogenically stored liquid hydrogen as fuel are studied intensely. The integration of superconducting motors and cables [9] brings potential improvements in electric aircraft’s power density and efficiency. Recent, highly topical activities in aviation research, therefore, consider using cryogenic media as a coolant [10], [11]. In addition to electric motors and cables, semiconductor devices such as Galliumnitride-high electron mobility transistor (GaN-HEMTs) and silicon metal-oxide semiconductor field effect transistors (Si-MOSFETs) can significantly benefit from cryogenic cooling, which reduces their ON-state resistance and may enhance dynamic behavior [12], [13], [14]

Since the electrical resistance of a semiconductor increases disproportionately with temperature, there exists a temperature where the generated heat in the semiconductor at a given current can no longer be dissipated. This leads to a positive feedback loop in which even an infinitesimally increasing temperature leads to disproportionately increasing losses and, as a result, to a thermal runaway (TR).

This phenomenon, which becomes increasingly pronounced with decreasing coolant temperature, is described in detail, theoretically analyzed, and experimentally proven in this article.

It is important to note that the effect described here deviates from the well-known Spirito-instability [15], [16], which has been analyzed in the past and is attributed to the positive temperature dependence of MOSFETs in the saturation region. In contrast, the TR described here occurs in the ohmic region.

II. PROBLEM FORMULATION

The basic setup of an exemplary power module is shown in Fig. 1(a). The power semiconductor chip is mounted on a dielectric substrate, typically based on ceramic material, to ensure both electrical insulation and low thermal resistance between chip and coolant. A GaN HEMT [17] is used as a semiconductor device to lay out the principle theory for the TR. Generally, the heat P_{th} conducted from the chip to the coolant increases linearly with the temperature difference ΔT between chip and coolant and the heat P_l generated by the losses in the semiconductor device increase over-proportionally with the chip or junction temperature T_j [18]. The losses $P_l(T_j)$ in a power semiconductor device are the sum of the conduction

Fig. 1. (a) Power module and definition of the chip-area specific thermal resistance R_{th}^A , the active chip area A_c , and temperature difference $\Delta T = T_j - T_c$. (b) Temperature-dependent ON-state resistance of a GaN HEMT (GS66516T) [19]: Measurement at $i_{ds} = 1$ A and $v_{gs} = 5$ V, (4) with two values of n , and a polynomial fit with $0.0003 \cdot T_j^2 + 0.226 \cdot T_j + 16.094$ and the values given in the data sheet.

losses $P_{cond}(T_j)$ and switching losses P_{sw} as follows:

$$P_1(T_j) = P_{cond}(T_j) + P_{sw}. \quad (1)$$

For unipolar semiconductors, the switching losses P_{sw} can be considered temperature independent with good approximation. This holds for HEMT, and for MOSFET operating in the first quadrant of the output characteristics. In most applications, the switching losses of GaN HEMT are negligible. Thus, for sake of clarity, these losses are neglected initially in the following analytical derivations.

The conduction losses P_{cond} are a function of the area-specific ON-resistance R_{ds}^A , often defined in the literature as the technology parameter with the designation $R_{ON} \cdot A$, [20] the active chip area A_c , and the current I_{ds} in the device as follows:

$$P_{cond}(T_j) = I_{ds}^2 \cdot \frac{R_{ds}^A(T_j)}{A_c}. \quad (2)$$

The temperature dependence of the ON-resistance of a n -channel unipolar device [see Fig. 1(b)] is linked with the electron mobility μ_e , the electron density n_e , and the elementary charge q as follows:

$$R_{ds}^A(T_j) \propto \frac{1}{q\mu_e(T_j)n_e(T_j)}. \quad (3)$$

For GaN-HEMT, the electron density is nearly constant down to liquid hydrogen temperatures and thus the ON-state resistance

is dominated by the electron mobility. The temperature dependence of the electron mobility is primarily governed by two scattering mechanisms [21], [22] as follows:

$$R_{ds}^A(T_j) \propto \frac{1}{\mu_e(T_j)} \propto T_j^n. \quad (4)$$

In the relevant temperature range (see Fig. 1), three superimposed phonon scattering mechanisms—piezo, acoustic, and optical polar scattering gain importance, leading to exponents between $n = 1.5$ and $n = 2.5$, depending on device technology [22]. As shown in [22], fitting an exponent of $n = 2$ is a good approximation for the mobility in a GaN-HEMT (2DEG) in the temperature range of 200 K to 300 K, while $n = 1.5$ becomes closer to experimental data at lower temperatures (see Fig. 1). This results in the power law scaling approach as shown in (6) utilizing a reference temperature T_0 —usually the room temperature—for which the ON-state resistance is specified in the data sheet.

$$R_{ds}^A(T_j) = R_{ds}^A(T_0) \cdot \frac{\mu_e(T_0)}{\mu_e(T_j)} = R_{ds}^A(T_0) \cdot \left(\frac{T_j}{T_0}\right)^n. \quad (5)$$

The junction temperature T_j can be written as the coolant temperature T_c plus the temperature difference ΔT between chip and coolant as follows:

$$R_{ds}^A(\Delta T) = R_{ds}^A(T_0) \cdot \left(\frac{T_c + \Delta T}{T_0}\right)^n. \quad (6)$$

The heat flux between chip and coolant is a function of the area-specific thermal resistance R_{th}^A , the chip area A_c , and the temperature difference ΔT as follows:

$$P_{th}(T_j) = A_c \cdot \frac{\Delta T}{R_{th}^A}. \quad (7)$$

The thermal resistance R_{th}^A is considered constant at first, initially neglecting the temperature-dependence of the thermal conductivity of the substrate materials (see Fig. 4) and of the heat transfer coefficient h at the boundary layer between heat sink and coolant.

To achieve thermal equilibrium, i.e., stationary conditions, the losses P_1 must be equal to the heat flux P_{th} conducted to the coolant as follows:

$$S_1 = \frac{P_{th}}{P_1} \stackrel{!}{=} 1. \quad (8)$$

Solving (8) for the current density J_{ds} in the chip results as follows:

$$J_{ds} = \frac{I_{ds}}{A_c} = \sqrt{\frac{\Delta T}{R_{ds}^A(T_0) \cdot R_{th}^A} \cdot \left(\frac{T_0}{T_c + \Delta T}\right)^n}. \quad (9)$$

In Fig. 2(a), the stationary chip current density J_{ds} fulfilling the equilibrium condition S_1 is shown for different coolant temperatures T_c as a function of the temperature difference ΔT . For room temperature cooling (dotted magenta) the well-known behavior of the current density increasing with temperature can be seen, whereby the curve follows a square root law in first approximation for typical ΔT lower than 150 K. With lower coolant temperatures T_c the equilibrium current increases

Fig. 2. (a) Current density J_{ds} for different coolant temperatures. The unstable operating region is shaded. (b) TR behavior for different coolant temperatures. (c) TR onset ΔT_{TR} depending on the temperature exponent n (LH₂: $T_c = 20 \text{ K}$, LN₂: $T_c = 77 \text{ K}$, RT: $T_c = 296 \text{ K}$).

due to the decreased ON-state resistance R_{ds}^A , however, a more pronounced current peak ($J_{ds,max}$) is formed. At temperatures beyond this peak, the possible current decreases despite an increasing temperature difference between chip and coolant due to the overproportional increase in losses P_1 . In this temperature range a positive feedback effect occurs that will lead to catastrophic failures in practical applications.

The temperature ΔT_{TR} corresponding to $J_{ds,max}$, i.e., the temperature difference above which the system enters TR, can be derived from (9) as follows:

$$\Delta T_{TR} = \frac{T_c}{n-1}. \quad (10)$$

This means that the onset point for TR depends only on two physical parameters: the coolant temperature T_c and the temperature dependence of the ON-resistance R_{ds}^A of the semiconductor chip, characterized by the power law exponent n .

For room temperature cooling ΔT_{TR} is well above 150 K [see Fig. 2(c)]. This is the reason why under normal cooling conditions, the TR phenomenon is irrelevant. For cryogenic coolant temperatures, however, the onset point is decreased substantially. In the case of liquid hydrogen cooling, i.e., at coolant temperatures T_c of 20 K, the TR's onset point is at an absolute junction temperature T_j of only 40 K. This means, that the remaining usable chip temperature swing is only 20 K! Under these cooling conditions, the transistor can carry three to four times the current compared to cooling at room temperature. However, operation is becoming more and more of a balancing act.

If temporary overload events (overcurrents) occur or if faults in the cooling circuit (e.g., bubbles in the cooling medium) lead to a temporarily increased ΔT , the tipping point for TR can quickly be exceeded. As soon as the system reaches an operating point to the right of the peak, i.e., to the right of the solid black line in Fig. 2(a), the chip temperature rises until destruction. This can be seen in Fig. 2(b). What is also very clearly visible is that the transition becomes sharper as the coolant temperature drops.

For room temperature (RT) cooling, it follows directly from Fig. 2(a), that the active chip area A_c required for a desired drain-source current I_{ds} can be greatly reduced by allowing a large temperature swing ΔT at the chip. This engineering trade-off is known from conventional cooling of power electronics. Decreasing the chip area decreases the cost, but also leads to increased losses in many applications. In addition, the larger temperature swing also results in reduced reliability of the power module packaging. For cryogenic cooling, Fig. 2(a) illustrates that small active chip areas significantly amplify the safety risk of thermal destruction. The resulting current densities are driven toward critical values at the onset point ΔT_{TR} , reducing the available temperature range before the chip enters the unstable region, where TR is triggered.

Switching losses: Significant switching losses impact the TR onset point. Independent of load current, the semiconductor will exhibit capacitive switching losses $P_{sw,C}$, which depend on A_C , the switching frequency f_s , the applied blocking voltage V_{DC} , and the area specific stored output charge Q_{OSS}^A .

In this case, the steady-state current J_{ds} at a given ΔT is as follows:

$$J_{ds}(\Delta T) = \sqrt{\frac{\Delta T - V_{DC} \cdot Q_{OSS}^A \cdot f_s \cdot R_{th}^A}{R_{ds}^A \cdot R_{th}^A \left(\frac{T_0}{T_c + \Delta T}\right)^n}}. \quad (11)$$

Fig. 3. Drain-source current density J_{ds} for different coolant temperatures taking capacitive switching losses $P_{sw,C}$ into account (LH₂: $T_c = 20$ K, LN₂: $T_c = 77$ K, RT: $T_c = 296$ K).

Fig. 4. Temperature dependence of the thermal conductivity λ of some inorganic packaging materials (RRR: “residual resistance value”) [23], [24], [25], [26], [27].

Again, J_{ds} shows a dedicated maximum at ΔT_{TR} as follows:

$$\Delta T_{TR} = \frac{T_c + n \cdot R_{th}^A \cdot f_s \cdot V_{DC} \cdot Q_{OSS}^A}{n - 1}. \quad (12)$$

Compared to the static case, ΔT_{TR} shifts to higher temperatures, as shown in Fig. 3, for a typical f_s of a traction inverter (20 kHz) and a typical dc/dc converter (100 kHz). These capacitive switching losses, therefore, act as a virtual increase of the coolant temperature T_c . Similar to higher T_c , the maximum J_{ds} decreases.

Temperature dependent R_{th}^A : The previous analysis assumed a constant thermal resistance of the packaging materials in the entire temperature range of $R_{th}^A = 0.5$ Kcm²/W. Although this assumption holds for conventional temperatures, under deep cryogenic conditions, the thermal conductivities of many inorganic materials increase significantly (see Fig. 4). In nearly all power electronic packaging structures, inorganic materials determine the thermal resistance from the chip to the heat sink.

Section A-A

Fig. 5. (a) Thermal finite element analysis results for different coolant temperatures and heat transfer coefficients h (LH₂: $T_c = 20$ K, LN₂: $T_c = 77$ K, RT: $T_c = 296$ K). (b) Results for temperature distribution in a power module and area-specific thermal resistances R_{th}^A at liquid hydrogen coolant temperatures (LH₂)—Simulated in ANSYS.

Therefore, R_{th}^A decreases at cryogenic temperatures (see Fig. 5). This influences the TR behavior (9). As a result, the current density J_{ds} at the chip can be further increased (see Fig. 6) at low temperatures.

With rising ΔT this enhancement diminishes due to increasing thermal conductivities [see Fig. 5(b)]. This means that the tipping point into the unstable temperature range can become even more pronounced.

Dynamics of the TR: The above considerations are based on stationary thermal conditions (9). To obtain more detailed information on the dynamics of the TR, the electrical model of the power semiconductor is coupled with a simple thermal model, as shown in Fig. 7(a). The dynamic behavior can then be described by the following differential equation with the thermal time constant $\tau_{th} = R_{th}C_{th}$:

$$\tau_{th} \frac{d}{dt} \Delta T(t) + \Delta T(t) = \left(J_{ds}(t)^2 R_{th}^A R_{ds}^A(T_0) \cdot \left(\frac{T_c}{T_0} \right)^n \left(1 + \frac{\Delta T(t)}{T_c} \right)^n \right). \quad (13)$$

Fig. 5 shows the temperature evolution over time for two different thermal time constants, each for the case of a current

Fig. 6. Drain-source current density J_{ds} (9) for different coolant temperatures and thermal resistances ($R_{th,0} = 0.5 \text{ Kcm}^2/\text{W}$; LH₂: $T_c = 20 \text{ K}$, LN₂: $T_c = 77 \text{ K}$, RT: $T_c = 296 \text{ K}$).

Fig. 7. (a) Equivalent circuit of the GS66516 T GaN-HEMT for thermal and electrical dynamic model. (b) Numeric solution of (13) for liquid nitrogen cooling ($T_c = 77 \text{ K}$), different thermal time constants τ_{th} , and current set points I_s as a share of the maximum allowable current $I_{ds,max}$ defined in Section II. An exponent n of 2 is used here for the simulation.

density 5% below the critical current density, exactly at the critical current density, and 5% above. Cooling using LN₂ is assumed, i.e., a coolant temperature of 77 K. A thermal time constant of 2 ms can be read from the Z_{th} -diagram for the relevant time range up to about one hundred milliseconds in the data sheet of the GaN-HEMT GS66516T [19]. This transistor is later used for the experimental investigations. It is evident that

Fig. 8. Measurement setup to test TR (GN₂: Gaseous nitrogen, LN₂: Liquid nitrogen, DUT: Device under test, A_{HS} : Base area of heat slug, d_{HS} : thickness of heat slug, d_{PUR} : thickness of polyurethane foam insulation), image sources GS66516T: [19], Graphtec GL840: [28].

the chip temperature approaches a stationary value at current densities up to the critical current density, as it is expected for operation in the stable region according to Fig. 2(a). However, if the critical current density is only slightly exceeded, the chip temperature runs away exponentially with a time constant that roughly corresponds to the thermal time constant.

III. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

Fig. 8 illustrates the measurement setup to validate the analytical model. A GaN-HEMT (GS66516 T) is chosen as the device under test (DUT). The DUT is soldered onto a double-layer printed circuit board (PCB) and is submerged in a Dewar vessel filled with liquid nitrogen at its normal boiling point (77 K).

Section II has shown that runaway occurs very quickly, but can be influenced by the thermal time constant. To demonstrate the effect experimentally, the thermal time constant is, therefore, increased by two measures compared to the bare chip. First, by mounting the component directly on a copper heat spreader (increase in C_{th} to approx. 12 J/K) and second, by surrounding the structure with thermal insulation out of polyurethane foam (increase in R_{th} to approx. 20 K/W). The resulting time constant τ_{th} is at 245 s.

The convective heat transfer coefficient at the boundary layer to boiling liquid nitrogen is highly nonlinear and dependent on the contact surface temperature T_c . Beyond the critical heat flux density q_{crit} , boiling regimes change from nucleate boiling to film boiling, leading to a strongly decreased heat transfer coefficient [29], [30]. By adding the thermal insulation, a series connection of the two thermal resistances $R_{th,pack} \approx 20 \text{ K/W}$ and $R_{th,N2} \approx 0.05 \text{ K/W} \dots 0.7 \text{ K/W}$ (see Fig. 8) is created, the

Fig. 9. (a) Temperature measurements and drain-source current i_{ds} (i_{ds} : calculated from v_{shunt} ; T_{vj} : calculated from v_{ds} measurement, and r_{ds} calibration measurement). (b) First time-derivative of the temperature measurement T_j indicating the TR onset.

latter corresponding to nucleate pool boiling [29]. In addition, a decreased heat flux density at the boundary layer to liquid nitrogen is achieved with the heat spreader. The rationale behind these conceptions is to mitigate the influence of the nonlinearity of the boiling heat transfer coefficient.

To monitor a potential change in the heat transfer coefficient at any point during the experiment the temperature at the contact surface T_c is tracked. The measurement points for the temperature data, utilizing platinum (PT1000) sensors, are indicated as red dots. In addition to the direct measurement of the junction temperature (T_j) via the temperature sensor, a second indirect measurement (T_{vj}) is conducted using the drain-source voltage v_{ds} in combination with the calibrated temperature dependence of the drain-source resistance r_{ds} according to Fig. 1. All measurement data is recorded with the data logger Graphtec GL840.

During the experiment, the DUT is turned ON with a fixed gate-source voltage v_{gs} of 5 V to ensure operation in the ohmic region. The drain-source currents i_{ds} (Fig. 9(a)—dotted line) are increased sequentially until the onset of TR is observed. Fig. 9(b) shows the time derivative of the measured junction

Fig. 10. (a) Comparison of simulated and measured drain-source resistance r_{ds} during TR. (b) Comparison of simulated and measured junction temperature T_j during TR.

temperature T_j , proving that steady state is reached at each step until the TR. After entering thermal runaway, the temperature rises increasingly fast, despite a constant chip current.

To verify the modeling approach laid out in Section II, Fig. 10(a) and (b) show the simulated results versus the measurement data for the parameters according to the measurement setup. Both figures demonstrate strong alignment with the analytical model, confirming its accuracy.

The comparison between the measured and simulated relationship of ΔT and i_{ds} in Fig. 10(b) shows noticeable deviations for $n = 1.5$ that can be attributed to the divergence of the r_{ds} values in the temperature range of 140 K to 250 K [see Fig. 1(b)]. In turn, this can also be seen in Fig. 10(a) (For the power law exponent of $n = 2$, the r_{ds} can be predicted well in the TR area at drain-source currents higher than 23 A, which results in good accuracy in the prediction of the junction temperature during the TR.

As a result, the prediction of the TR must be conducted for each specific device, based on its temperature behavior n and the theory presented in this article.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this study a theoretical description of the critical issue of TR in cryogenic power electronics is described. An experimental validation is provided that confirms the prediction from semiconductor physics. A simple way of estimating the onset temperature of TR is presented and tested for liquid nitrogen cooling. It is shown, that TR onset temperature is drastically decreased at cryogenic temperatures. The understanding of the TR effect described here is crucial for advancing the development of safe cryogenic power electronics needed for the future of electric aviation. Unlike at conventional coolant temperatures, at cryogenic temperatures the temperature gradient across the chip cannot be freely selected as a design parameter. It is essential to determine the critical temperature gradient—hence, the onset point of the thermal runaway—based on the presented theory and the specific temperature dependency of the semiconductor switch. Then, a sufficient safety margin from the “onset point” must be considered during the thermal design. Further research should be conducted by quantifying the dynamics of the TR and possible mitigation strategies.

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